

ISic3102

I.Sicily inscription 3102

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331429

1. [ύπατία] Άλβεί-
2. [νου λαμπρο (τάτου) ²⁷νέου²⁷]
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645450

PHI 331429

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0880

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Orsi, P. 1896. Gli scavi a S. Giovanni a Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 10: 1-59. At 33 no.334

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3102. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388137>